

CROSS-CULTURAL ANALYSIS OF WESTERN AND RUSSIAN NONVERBAL MEANS OF COMMUNICATION

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Cross-cultural communication can be considered as a sort of communication that aims to share information across different cultures and social groups. Within globalization, communication among countries has become quite common. There's no denying that the knowledge of varied cultures plays a significant role in intercultural communication.

William Shakespeare has famous words about nonverbal communication “There is language in her eye, her cheek, her lip. Nay, her foot speaks.” American psychologist Albert Mehrabian, a pioneer researcher of body language within the 1950s, found that the overall impact of a message is about 7% verbal (words only) and 38% vocal (including tone of voice, inflexion and other sounds) and 55% nonverbal [Mehrabian 2007: 78]. Therefore, the importance of nonverbal communication is evident.

Nonverbal communication isn't just visual communication, but it is also associated with transmitting knowledge. Larry A. Samovar (2004) defined nonverbal communication as the messages that are transmitted as intentional and unintentional behaviours, which have a good range, like facial expressions, eye contact, gestures, postures, space and distance. To induce complete understanding and avoid any misunderstandings of nonverbal meanings we should always bear in mind various factors, especially cultural differences.

Nonverbal communication is deeply rooted in culture. Cultural values and norms influence nonverbal communication and determine what quite nonverbal behaviour is acceptable. On the other hand, nonverbal communication may be a mirror, reflecting different cultures. In this article, we'll use the comparative method to debate several nonverbal factors utilized in daily life, which can cause

misunderstanding and awkwardness for Westerners and Russians in cross-cultural communication.

1. FACIAL EXPRESSIONS

Feeling happy, all over the world we smile, while the emotions of enjoyment, sadness, fear, anger and surprise are just presupposed to be expressed similarly: the frequency and context of using these facial expressions vary from culture to culture.

Expressing a negative attitude toward something in the presence of others is uncharacteristic for Americans, which is the reason for the frequent use of a smile in the process of communication. National American tradition says no matter what happens, you need to smile (keep smiling). This phenomenon is called the American smile code [Wierzbicka, 1999]. According to the "code" described above, representatives of American culture do not show their bad mood and their problems to other people. They do not see the point in this and consider it wrong concerning their interlocutors.

It is customary for Americans to smile when looking at children or animals. 90% of Americans smile while greeting.

Russian culture, by L. Visson's point, is rather characterized by a pessimistic attitude associated with the psychologically difficult history of Russia. If a Russian smiles, this, as a rule, is a manifestation of sincerity and a good mood [Visson 2005: 115-116].

Americans predominantly smile with "teeth". While smiling, they show their upper and lower teeth simultaneously. Russian writer M. Gorky, having visited America in the 1930s, wrote: "The first thing you see on an American's face is teeth." Russians smile more modestly, with "lips", sometimes showing only the bottom row of teeth. The American smile in execution resembles the Russian grin, that is, the demonstration of teeth by animals, and is evaluated with caution often disapprovingly, it may be considered artificial, demonstrative, insincere.

2. EYE CONTACT

In interpersonal communication, it's indispensable to stay in eye contact with others. In fact, in several nations and cultures, the utilization of eye contact is sort of different. Sometimes, they have opposite meanings. Within the communication among Western countries, taking America and England for instance, straight eye contact may be a sign showing upright and honesty. A proverb in Western countries goes, "Never trust people who can't look in your eyes." Without straight eye contact, the person is going to be considered timid, not confident and impolite. In England and France, gentlemen stare at the feminine to point out appreciation, which may be a publicly recognized cultural value. According to a scientific study, the typical length of eye contact is 2.95 seconds, and therefore the average duration of the time two people look at one another is 1.18 seconds (Argyle, 1994). On the contrary, in Russian communication, this system causes hostility towards the beholder.

These differences can cause miscommunication within multicultural communication. Being conscious of different cultures and showing respect, and understanding of the various implications of eye contact in several cultural contexts is friendly to others and also as beneficial to one's part.

3. SILENCE

According to American communicating norms, you can stay silent for a while even in a big company. That will not cause others to make you talk to the interlocutor. Moreover, it will not attract attention to you at all. Americans have no concept of "embarrassing silence." At the table, the conversation should not be conducted by everyone simultaneously and continuously.

4. GESTURES

Gestures are the movement of fingers to speak with one another and express ideas. They can often take the place of verbal language to start and stop communication, sometimes explaining and strengthening what people express. Some researchers from Levy Bruhl, Lucien (Lucien, 2010) showed that at the initial time, while tribes of India had different verbal languages, they might communicate and understand one another through gestures. In modern society, the

gesture remains an efficient and irreplaceable way of communication. In cross-culture communication, people with language barriers more often use gestures to precise something. The utilization of gestures is flexible and filled with various meanings, particularly in a different culture.

For Russians, a raised thumb symbolizes the highest rating. In the USA, this gesture may mean - everything goes well or - the desire to catch a passing car, and if the finger is sharply thrown up, this is an obscene expression. How the finger is thrown (at least until recently) did not matter in Russian culture, but in America, this detail radically modifies what was said.

Sometimes even a slight change in a gesture can completely change its meaning. So in England, it happened with two fingers, index and middle, raised. If at the same time the palm is turned towards the interlocutor this is a terrible insult. And if the palm is turned towards oneself, this is the first letter of the word “victory” (victory). We have often seen how well-known politicians expressed their joy with this gesture, and we also remember the forest of “Vs” flying up over the heads of their supporters who greeted them.

Also, the familiar gesture for Russians, meaning "I'm fed up with this" (running the edge of the palm along the neck), is never used in the United States in this sense.

Some gestures may overlap in Russian and American cultures. So, counting is done with the help of fingers, but the Russians bend them, starting with the pinkie. And the Americans unbend them, with the thumb, or count, touching alternately with the index finger of one hand to the fingers of the open palm of the other hand. In both countries, a handshake is a sign of greeting, but in the United States, it is usually short and vigorous with arms extended at full length. In Russia, the arms are bent and the more respect, the longer the handshake.

Calling with a bendable index finger is acceptable in the USA, but not very decent in Russia. Among Russians, it is considered indecent to point at something that is at close range with the index finger. This gesture is considered too authoritarian, and dominant, therefore, if it is necessary, for example, to point out a

word to a student in a book opened in front of him, the teacher often shows the middle finger, which seems indecent to Americans. Whistling and stamping your feet at a concert or other public event is considered a sign of approval in the US.

The conclusion is obvious: if the exact meanings of gestures are unknown, it is better to exclude them altogether when communicating with foreigners. These gestures are either not understood or have a different interpretation.

5. POSTURES

Postures refer to transmitting messages through body movement. While communicating, postures could tell us about social station, religion, desire and intention. The recognition of one posture in comparison with another and the emotion conveyed by a given posture seems to be largely determined by culture [Samovar 2004: 168]. During a communication, we may unconsciously put our soles to others while sticking one leg over the opposite. It may be considered as disrespect for Russians, whereas among Americans it's simply how to point out feeling relaxed.

Another posture Americans usually use is shrugging shoulders. It can be interpreted that they are innocent and have no secret to conceal. But in Russia, it can be expressed as indifference and ignorance.

For Americans, smartness and straight posture are very important. Just like a smile, it is intended to indicate good health (which is of great importance) and the absence of problems. Americans try to look sporty and energetic. American elderly people are smarter and more well-groomed than Russians. Americans, to a greater extent than Russians, are characterized by a straight posture when sitting, they do not bend as low when eating as Russians.

Americans can sit in transport and office with their ankle on the knee of the other leg (the "four" position), this position is considered acceptable. You can put your feet on the table in certain situations.

In Russia, putting your feet on furniture is indecent. The Americans, on the other hand, do not see anything indecent in this. Therefore, they calmly settle down

even at official events in a way that suits them. They do this not because they want to offend us with something, but because it is acceptable in their country.

In general, the examples I have given demonstrate the need to study the features of both verbal and non-verbal communication. This knowledge is extremely necessary for specialists in the field of teaching language, who have to practice the interaction of people of different cultures.

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